

How Are Women with Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder and a History of Offending Supported in the English & Welsh CJS?

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Abstract

Evidence suggests rates of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) are disproportionately high among women with a history of offending. Evidence also suggests that if women were treated for their ADHD, criminality could be reduced by approximately 41%. Despite this, these women are under researched, underdiagnosed and under treated.

Semi-structured interviews of four professionals and practitioners who work around these women were used to investigate the awareness, attitudes, and the provision of support for these women.

The findings reveal a pervasive lack of awareness about ADHD in women, compounded by inadequate training and persistent stigma and misconceptions within the CJS. The study highlights how these issues result in poor identification and support for women with ADHD, exacerbating their challenges within the CJS. Additionally, the research uncovers the impact of prioritizing other factors such as substance misuse, domestic abuse, and child welfare over the ADHD needs of these women.

The insights gained underscore the necessity for comprehensive and mandatory training tailored to ADHD, improved screening and identification processes, and enhanced support mechanisms within the CJS. This research addresses a critical gap in the literature and provides a foundational step towards more effective interventions and policy developments to better support women with ADHD in the criminal justice system.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is a neurodevelopmental condition characterised by inattentiveness, hyperactivity, and impulsivity (American Psychiatric Association, 2022). It also often involves symptoms such as emotional dysregulation, working memory deficits, risk taking behaviours and executive dysfunction (American Psychiatric Association, 2022). People with ADHD are also at greater risk than the general population of participating in criminal behaviour; and those with ADHD who do take part in criminal behaviour are more likely to start younger, become involved with the police younger and have a higher rate of recidivism than their non-ADHD counterparts (Young and Cocallis, 2021). It must be mentioned that most people with ADHD will not go on to offend, but the overrepresentation of ADHD in the criminal justice system (CJS) and high rates of recidivism highlights the significance of support for individuals with ADHD with a history of offending.

Additionally, recent research has suggested that, once believed to be a predominantly male condition, ADHD presents in women and men at a more comparable rate than once thought (Hinshaw et al., 2022). Furthermore, women with ADHD represent a particularly vulnerable population, often facing unique challenges that are compounded when they intersect with the CJS (Young et al., 2018; Young et al., 2020). ADHD in women is significantly underdiagnosed and misunderstood, largely due to the understanding of ADHD being developed from studies focused on the stereotypical image of ADHD: the hyperactive young boy (Hinshaw et al., 2022). Women with ADHD often exhibit different symptoms, such as inattentiveness and internalizing behaviours, which can be less conspicuous and therefore more likely to go unrecognized (Kistler, 2022). This discrepancy in symptom presentation contributes to a delayed or missed diagnosis, leading to a range of untreated ADHD symptoms that can significantly impair daily functioning and increase vulnerability of interactions with the CJS (Young and Cocallis, 2021; Kistler, 2022). Therefore, support specifically tailored to this population is essential. However, there is a significant gap in the research on the support available to women with ADHD and a history of offending and the awareness of ADHD in women in criminal justice settings. This research will seek to address this gap by exploring the awareness and support available for women with ADHD and a history of offending. For the purpose of this research, support will refer to the safeguarding, treatment, and adjustments which aim at accommodating the unique needs of individuals and enhance their ability to function effectively in various settings.

The central aim of this project has been to explore how women with ADHD and a history of offending are safeguarded and treated. The following objective have been produced in order to ensure that this project achieves this aim:

1. To explore the multifaceted challenged associated with women with ADHD and a history of offending.
2. To understand the awareness of and attitudes towards ADHD in women with a history of offending in the CJS.
3. To investigate the support that is available to women with ADHD and a history of offending by exploring what types of support are available, how accessible the support is and the effectiveness of this support.

Overall, this research aims to contribute to a more informed and responsive CJS that can better meet the needs of women with ADHD. By exploring the multifaceted challenges they face, assessing current levels of awareness and attitudes, and evaluating the support available to them, this dissertation seeks to pave the way for improvements that can enhance their well-being and reduce their risk of reoffending. This research is timely and necessary, given the increasing recognition of ADHD in adults and the pressing need to address the specific challenges faced by women within the justice system. Through a deeper understanding of these issues, we can work towards a more equitable and effective system of support for women with ADHD in the CJS.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The primary objective of this literature review is to provide a critical overview of the literature and current state of knowledge surrounding women with ADHD and a history of offending, focusing on how they are safeguarded and treated in the CJS. Specifically, it will seek to address the unique needs of this population, and the availability and effectiveness of safeguards and support mechanism in addressing these needs. By evaluating the literature, this review aims to identify gaps in the literature to assert where this research will fit in to improve the understanding the multifaceted challenged this population often experience, what support systems are in place, and what needs to be done to improve the support. Understanding and addressing the needs of this vulnerable population are paramount to promoting fair and equitable outcomes within the CJS.

In selecting literature for this review, specific inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied to ensure relevance and rigor. Studies included all refer to ADHD, most of which focus on adulthood but some reference adolescents or youth as there is less research on adult ADHD. All studies are relevant in presenting the struggles which women with ADHD may face in the CJS, however, they are not all limited to female participants or in the context of the CJS due to the lack of research on these topics. The literature included is all peer-reviewed; published from 2014-2024; and have English publications available. There will also be no specific inclusion criteria for the majority of the review regarding the location the research was carried out in to provide a comprehending overview. However, when discussing the specific safeguarding and treatment methods in place in the CJS, the review will only reference research in UK. The exclusion criteria are as follows: not focussing on ADHD; on children below 14-years-old; is not peer-reviewed; does not have publications available in English; publications that are older than 10-years-old; and research not in the UK on safeguarding and treatments in place in the CJS. However, the peer-reviewed criterion will be partially ignored when discussing the support available for ADHD in the CJS in the UK due to the lack of literature meaning some grey literature must be referenced to gain a full understanding of it.

2.2 Research Context regarding ADHD & the CJS

ADHD presents a complex issue within the CJS. Evidence suggests that there is an increased rate of offending among individuals with ADHD (Young and Cocallis, 2021), therefore it is unsurprising that ADHD is overrepresented in the CJS (Young et al., 2015; Farooq et al., 2016; Baggio et al., 2018). Two

meta-analyses found that 25.5% of adult prisoners met the criteria for ADHD when assessed using a clinical interview (Young et al., 2015; Baggio et al., 2018). Another study used a self-report scale based on the DSM-IV criteria and found that 41% of adult female prisoners met the criteria for ADHD (Farooq et al., 2016). In comparison, 2.5% of the general population have ADHD (Song et al., 2021). This indicates the large scale of the issue as the prevalence of ADHD within the prison population exceeds that of the general population by at least tenfold.

Additionally, research has found rates of recidivism are also higher among individuals with ADHD. For instance, a 15-year follow-up study investigating 106 former male youth prisoners found that offenders with ADHD reoffend faster, showed a higher rate of recidivism, and received a higher rate of further custodial sentences in comparison to their non-ADHD counterparts (Phillipp-Wiegmann et al., 2018). Additional research has found that ADHD is a predictor of violent reoffending in young offenders (Hertz et al., 2022). These studies, however, were limited by small, male-only samples reducing the generalisability, especially to the present study as it focuses on women with ADHD who may differ in their symptom presentations (Quinn and Madhoo, 2014; Babinski, 2024). However, one meta-analysis on mental disorder and women's recidivism found that ADHD is one of the mental disorders associated with certain symptom clusters that are commonly found in individuals who have a higher risk of recidivism (Pettersen et al., 2024). While the exact risk posed by ADHD in women remains unclear, these findings suggest a potential link between ADHD and recidivism in women, warranting further investigation. This high prevalence of ADHD in the CJS along with high rates of recidivism, indicates the need for identification and treatment of ADHD both within the CJS and prior to CJS interactions in order to reduce offending rates among this population.

2.3 Gender

Historically, the existing body of research on ADHD primarily centred on male populations (Young et al., 2020; Hinshaw et al., 2022). Consequently, scholarly attention devoted to the intersection of ADHD and womanhood is notably limited and female presentations of ADHD have been significantly overlooked in research and clinical settings (Young et al., 2020). There has been a recent increase in research on ADHD in women (Quinn and Madhoo, 2014; Young et al., 2020; Hinshaw et al., 2022), however there is still a lot of catching-up to do. The research that does exist on women with ADHD has established that although the prevalence of ADHD in boys is almost double that of girls, by adulthood, prevalence rates are almost equal (Hinshaw et al., 2022). This demonstrates the diagnostic issue amongst women and girls with ADHD. Women and girls with ADHD are frequently not diagnosed, misdiagnosed, or diagnosed later in life (Young et al., 2020; Hinshaw et al., 2022; Morgan,

2023). This is likely to be due to a multitude of reasons. Firstly, as the research has predominantly been on males, the understanding of ADHD largely comes from male stereotypes meaning women who do not fit these stereotypes often fall under the radar (Hinshaw et al., 2022). Moreover, women are more likely than men to present inattentive symptoms of ADHD and are more likely to mask ADHD symptoms due to the societal expectations that encourage women to 'fit in' and please others, which makes it more difficult to identify ADHD (Kistler, 2022). This demonstrates a need for awareness on ADHD in women in order to effectively identify and treat it.

As previously stated, women have unique symptom presentations and experiences of ADHD to men, and these must be understood in order to treat them (Babinski, 2024). As well as presenting more inattentive symptoms of ADHD than men, research has found women are more likely to have comorbid mental health conditions than men such as anxiety, depression, schizophrenia, and borderline personality disorder (Young et al., 2020). They are also more likely to self-harm and present suicidal behaviours than their male counterparts (Giupponi et al., 2018; Septier et al., 2019; Austgulen et al., 2023). These gender differences present unique challenges which are of a high importance and suggests that the vulnerability among individuals with ADHD may be greater among women (Ottoen et al., 2019). Understanding them is essential to better support and treat ADHD in women.

2.4 Risk Factors Associated with ADHD

Research has identified several key risk factors associated with ADHD, especially in the context of the CJS (Mohr-Jensen and Steinhausen, 2016; Chaplin et al., 2022). Among these, self-harm and suicidal ideation, substance use disorder (SUD), and the propensity for false confessions in individuals with ADHD are of particular concern (Gudjonsson et al., 2021; Austgulen et al., 2023; Young et al., 2023). These three are of significant interest as inadequate safeguarding for these risks could result in grave health consequences or unjust outcomes for individuals with ADHD involved in the CJS.

2.4.1 Suicidal Spectrum Behaviours

Suicidal spectrum behaviours (SSB) are a range of self-destructive behaviours such as self-harm, suicidal ideation, suicidal plans, attempted suicide and completed suicide (Austgulen et al., 2023). Recent research has found an association between ADHD and SSB (Septier et al., 2019; Austgulen et al., 2023). A systematic review and a meta-analysis on ADHD and SSB found that individuals with ADHD are at greater risk of SSB than their non-ADHD counterparts (Septier et al., 2019; Austgulen et al., 2023). These studies also both show that women are more likely than their male counterparts to

show SSB. Men have more completed suicides, however, women with ADHD more likely than their male counterparts to report self-harm and non-fatal suicidal behaviours. These gender differences could be accredited to the higher rates of comorbid mental disorders in women with ADHD than men (Young et al., 2020) and the diagnostic delays that women often face leaving which can have significant impacts on women's mental health and self-esteem (Morgan, 2023).

Findings of increased SSB in individuals with ADHD have been replicated across criminal justice settings too (McCarthy et al., 2019). Without the addition of ADHD as a variable, SSB are found to be more frequently occurring in prisons than the general population (Yasmeen et al., 2023). This is likely due to the higher rate of mental disorders in prisons, as well as the stressors associated with prison such as isolation and a lack of mental health support which may exacerbate these issues (Goomany, 2015). There is a lack of research concerning SSB in prisoners with ADHD, however, one study carried out on prisoners found that those with neurodevelopmental disorders were more likely than those without to report SSB (McCarthy et al., 2019). Despite this, the study did not focus solely on ADHD and therefore it is unclear how generalisable these results are to prisoners with ADHD specifically. Additionally, the small, male-only sample also limits the generalisability of this research. No research could be found on a population of female prisoners with ADHD surrounding SSB, further reinforcing the need for additional research on women with ADHD in the CJS. Given that SSB is more frequently reported in people with ADHD than their non-ADHD counterparts, particularly women (Septier et al., 2019; Austgulen et al., 2023), and that it is also more frequently reported in the prison population than the general population, it is reasonable to infer that women with ADHD in the CJS may also exhibit a high prevalence of SSB. However, additional research should be carried out to address this gap.

2.4.2 False Confessions

The relationship between ADHD and the risk of false confessions is a critical area of concern in the CJS. A false confession occurs when an individual who is completely innocent of a crime confesses to it (Gudjonsson et al., 2018). Although research on this domain is limited, existing studies have found evidence suggesting ADHD can be a significant predictor of false confessions. One study focussing on juveniles and young people aged 14-24, found that individuals with ADHD are more prone to police interrogation and giving false confessions (Gudjonsson et al., 2016). It also found that the younger the individuals, the more likely they were to give a false confession. Moreover, males were more likely than females to give a false confession. However, the applicability of these findings is limited due to the narrow age range of the sample. Another study, which exclusively sampled male offenders, also identified ADHD as a predictor of false confessions (Gudjonsson et al., 2021). The gender specificity of

this sample, however, restricts the generalizability of its conclusions, particularly for studies focusing on women with ADHD such as the current study. Additionally, both studies examine a range of disorders alongside ADHD, making it challenging to isolate the impact of ADHD alone. Despite this, the frequent comorbidity of other mental disorders with ADHD, especially among women (Young et al., 2020; Young and Cocallis, 2021), underscores the value of these findings. However, more research is needed address the gap of knowledge concerning adult women with ADHD and false confessions.

Additional research has found that individuals with ADHD are more likely to respond with 'don't know' instead of giving a 'direct explanation' response to a question that individuals would usually be able to answer correctly (Gudjonsson and Young, 2021). This is likely to be attributed to weak source monitoring and poor memory, which may lead to individuals with ADHD being vulnerable to misinforming the police when "confidence in their memory is undermined by the interviewing strategy" (Gudjonsson and Young, 2021, p.5). Also, false confessions are likely to be the product of contextual and situational risk factors as well as personal ones (ADHD); meaning the likelihood of an individual with ADHD giving a false confession may exacerbated by peer-pressure, police pressure, the influence of substances, duration of interview, or leading questions for example (Young and Cocallis, 2021).

2.4.3 Substance-Use Disorder (SUD)

Substance abuse and substance use disorder is also an area of concern involving individuals with ADHD. SUD is one of the most common comorbid disorders for individuals with ADHD (Young et al., 2023) and research has consistently indicated that individuals with ADHD are more likely to suffer from SUD than those without ADHD (Breyer et al., 2014; Young and Sedgwick, 2015; Ottosen et al., 2016). Research has also found that women with ADHD have a higher risk of developing SUD than their male counterparts. One study found that women with ADHD without comorbidities were at higher risk of developing SUD as well as those with comorbidities such as conduct disorder (Ottosen et al., 2016). This shows that the association between SUD and ADHD cannot be explained solely by the common occurrence of comorbid mental disorders. Other studies have corroborated these findings revealing sex differences in ADHD and comorbid SUD (Ottosen et al., 2019; Castellano-Garcia et al., 2022). However, many of these studies on ADHD and SUD are limited by their adolescent samples, which leaves open the possibility that SUD may develop later in life (Breyer et al., 2014; Castellano-Garcia et al., 2022). SUD is also rife in prisons, with one meta-analysis estimating 30% of male prisoners and 51% of female prisoners to suffer from some type of drug use disorder (Fazel et al., 2017), indicating that prisoners with ADHD are likely to be markedly vulnerable. Research has

confirmed this with one study finding around 60% of prisoners with ADHD also having SUD (Chaplin et al., 2022). Unfortunately, none of this research on prisoners with ADHD includes women in its samples, therefore limiting the application of the research to the female population. It can be inferred however, that female prisoners with ADHD are of particular vulnerability to SUD due to their increased risk in the general population and the increased with within prisons (Ottosen et al., 2016; Fazel et al., 2017).

2.5 Awareness, Safeguarding and Treatment in the CJS

Once ADHD has been identified in an individual within the CJS, there is an opportunity for support to be administered. Depending on the stage in the CJS, what this support looks like can vary. As discussed previously, individuals with ADHD are at an increased risk of giving false confessions, SSB, and SUD along with other things (Gudjonsson et al., 2016; Ottosen et al., 2016; Septier et al., 2019), and therefore the safeguarding and treatment of them in the CJS is essential.

2.5.1 Awareness and Identification

Prior to the discussion of research surrounding the safeguarding and treatment of ADHD in the CJS however, the awareness of ADHD, particularly in women, must be discussed. As stated previously, ADHD is largely under- and mis-diagnosed, especially in the CJS, and especially in women (Young et al., 2018; Young et al., 2020). Therefore, awareness of ADHD is vital in order for people with ADHD to be identified, diagnosed and receive the support they need (Young et al., 2018). However, research has shown that attitudes and awareness of ADHD within the CJS generally is poor. One piece of research carried out by the Criminal Justice Joint inspection (CJJI, 2021), which reviewed neurodiversity in the CJS, found that the majority of staff in police, prison and probation services had received little or no training on neurodiversity and any awareness that they had tended to come from previous jobs or personal experiences and was not extensive. Although this study is not peer-reviewed, it involves systematic and rigorous reviews conducted by professionals in the field of criminal justice and adhere to high standards of evidence and analysis. While they do not go through the same peer-review process as most academic literature, this review is worth discussing due to the valuable insight it provides on attitudes towards and awareness of neurodivergence in the CJS which is otherwise under researched. The general consensus of this research highlights a widespread ignorance towards ADHD and the view of ADHD is an additional burden of which ties up resources. This view is likely to be exhausted by staff shortages and a lack of training. This is highly problematic as research based on an expert consensus concluded that awareness of criminal justice staff was essential in order to shift and reform the stereotypes and misconceptions that they might have of

ADHD and to improve the outcomes of offenders with ADHD (Young et al., 2018). However, this research has focused mainly on awareness regarding ADHD in men and therefore it cannot represent awareness of ADHD in women with a history of offending (Young et al., 2018; CJI, 2021). Due to the lack of overall awareness of how ADHD presents in women (Young et al., 2020), it is likely that the awareness of ADHD in women with a history of offending amongst staff in the CJS is even worse than that of ADHD in men.

The identification of individuals in the CJS with ADHD, who have not yet been diagnosed, is reliant on staff awareness of ADHD and offender self-awareness of ADHD (Young et al., 2018); and the support for these individuals for their ADHD is reliant on the identification of it. This indicates the importance of awareness. However, in addition to the lack of training and awareness, there is also a lack screening tools implemented to aid ADHD identification. Research carried out by Young et al. (2018) was conducted using an expert consensus meeting on the identification and treatment of offenders with ADHD in prison. This study found that in most prison institutions, the primary mental health screening that they receive on admission to the prison does not include questions relate to ADHD symptoms. However, it does not provide much insight into female offenders with ADHD and does not refer to identification at any other stage in the CJS, therefore limiting its generalisability. Recently, however, grey literature has indicated a screening pilot for ADHD has been released by the City of London Police due to the growing recognition of ADHD, particularly undiagnosed ADHD, in the CJS (City of London Police, 2023). This is a positive advancement in ADHD services in the CJS and could lead to ADHD being recognised, supported, and treated better in the CJS, which could lead to a reduction in recidivism among this demographic. As of now, the reliability and validity of the screening pilot is unclear, and it is only in place in the City of London Police and as no official research has been published on its efficacy. The lack of research on the identification of ADHD in individuals throughout the CJS highlights a need for this gap to be filled, especially regarding female offenders.

2.5.2 Arrest & Detention (Police)

Due to the increased risk among individuals with ADHD of giving false confessions, SSB, and SUD, they must be sufficiently safeguarded by the police while being arrested, detained and questioned. There is also evidence to suggest individuals with neurodiverse conditions, including ADHD, are more likely to react disruptively in police custody and find police interviews challenging emotionally and practically, as well as give false confessions (Gudjonsson et al., 2016; Freckelton, 2019). Therefore, training, and safeguarding measures specific to ADHD within police custody are essential to ensure evidence is of sound quality and to reduce the stress and overwhelm of the experience for the offender/suspect with ADHD as much as possible. However, there is little research indicating how

often such support is administered in the UK, and as already established, there is little to no training on neurodiverse conditions (CJI, 2021).

One safeguarding measure used is appropriate adults (AA). Under Police and Criminal Evidence Act 1984 Code C, vulnerable individuals and minors are entitled to an AA while being detained or interviewed by the police “to safeguard the rights, entitlements and welfare” of these individuals (S1). An individual with ADHD, in police custody, would be considered a vulnerable person, and therefore would be entitled to an AA. It is unclear, however, how commonly this is implemented, and it would only be able to be implemented when ADHD is recognised, which it often is not, reiterating the importance of awareness and screening. There is also research to suggest that sometimes the police do not implement the AA safeguard in cases involving a vulnerable person (Dehghani, 2016; Cummins, 2019). One study found that a lack of implementing AAs might be explained by identification issues as well as how police officers interpret and define ‘vulnerable’ (Dehghani, 2016). However, as this research was carried out a while ago, it is unclear whether these ambiguities have been addressed by this point. Moreover, both of these studies did not discuss the implementation of AAs to individuals with ADHD specifically and therefore are also limited by this.

2.6 Trial & Sentencing (Court)

There is a lack of research on the court and trial procedures involving defendants with ADHD in the UK. This gap must be addressed in order to evaluate the current system and assess whether it needs to be adapted to better safeguard individuals with ADHD and therefore lead to more just outcomes for them. Freckelton (2019) asserted that ADHD should be considered in reference to fitness to stand trial; the partial defence of diminished responsibility, depending on the nature of the crime and severity of the ADHD in the individual; and is very relevant in sentencing. He also stated that ADHD could be used to explain “unusual conduct in court, which otherwise might be misinterpreted” (p.834). This unusual conduct might take the form of lateness, distractibility, daydreaming, disorganisation, and may appear unconcerned due to these factors (Berryessa, 2017). However, these factors are actually symptoms and should be recognised as such in order to ensure the defendant is not treated harsher because of them.

Secondly, judges and magistrates' awareness and attitudes will also affect whether or not a defendant's ADHD is considered sufficiently or not. As the CJI (2021) found that the majority of staff in the police, prison and probation services had received little or no training, it is likely that this is the same for Judges and Magistrates, especially magistrates as they are untrained lay people. However, there is a lack of research on this area specifically and therefore the training and awareness of judges

and magistrates cannot be assessed properly. It is important however, that levels of awareness within court are understood as life altering decisions are made by judges and magistrates.

2.7 Serving Sentences (Prison & Probation)

Post-court services, such as prison and probation, provide an opportunity to not only support individuals and their ADHD but also treat it due to the longer duration of contact at this stage of the CJS. However, there is very little research on this area as well. This literature search found nothing to suggest there are any screening, diagnosis procedures, treatments or safeguarding measures specifically for ADHD in UK prisons other than that carried out by Young et al. (2018) as previously mentioned. Other studies have also reported a lack of support or a lack of research on support measures too (Chaplin et al., 2022). It can be assumed therefore, that ADHD is inadequately dealt with or completely ignored in most cases in prison (CJJI, 2021). The CJJI report (2021) indicates this. This can be observed when the report mentions one interviewee who had declared his ADHD, autism and PTSD on arrival to the prison, yet he said that he received no accommodations, support or treatment for his conditions and did not even think the prison staff were aware of his conditions.

2.8 Conclusion

This literature review highlights significant issues surrounding women with ADHD in the CJS. Key risk factors among this population includes SSBs, SUD, comorbid mental disorders, and false confessions, underscoring the increased vulnerability of women with ADHD in the CJS (Gudjonsson et al., 2021; Austgulen et al., 2023; Young et al., 2023). Due to this increased vulnerability, awareness, identification, and support for these individuals within the CJS is essential. However, there is a lack of research on this area, and the research that does exist suggests that there is a lack of awareness, poor identification tools, and a lack of support available at all stages of the CJS (Dehghani, 2016; Young et al., 2018; CJJI, 2021). Moreover, this research is majorly concerning ADHD in male offenders and therefore is limited in its generalisability to women with ADHD and a history of offending (Young et al., 2018; CJJI, 2021). Therefore, the present study will aim to address this gap in the literature by exploring the unique and multifaceted challenges women with ADHD and a history of offending face, the awareness of ADHD in women in the CJS, and the support mechanism in place for these women.

Chapter 3: Methodology

3.1 Research Approach

The research question for this study “How are women with ADHD and a history of offending are supported?” will be best answered by qualitative data due to exploratory and multifaceted nature. Therefore, the methodology will be qualitative. Qualitative methods allowed for a holistic understanding of the support landscape and uncovered unexpected insights. For this qualitative research, I used an interpretivist epistemology which suggests that the knowledge that we gain cannot exist independent of the researcher’s interpretation of reality and is therefore also accepts a relative ontological position (Snape and Spencer, 2003; Levers, 2013). It can also be argued that it is impossible to completely separate biases and subjectivity from research collected on the social world (Blaikie and Priest 2017) and therefore this can be embraced with the use of qualitative approaches rather than ignored by quantitative ones.

Due to the subjectivity of qualitative approaches and the social world, my positionality as a researcher must be mentioned. I am a woman with ADHD myself and therefore find myself in a unique position of both researcher and subject. While I do not have a history of offending and therefore cannot relate to many of the complex issues that come with it, I can relate to and understand many of the complex issues and experiences that come with being a woman with ADHD. This could be a strength as my personal experience as a woman with ADHD may provide significant intel and a nuanced perspective into this area. However, it could also be considered a negative as my pre-existing assumptions on the area may affect the research findings. I am conscious of the importance of my self-awareness in regard to mitigating these pre-existing assumptions and biases. I aimed to maintain a neutral perspective during data collection and analysis, yet it is crucial to acknowledge that the complete elimination of researcher bias is unrealistic. Therefore, transparency regarding the potential influence of my assumptions is essential.

3.2 Sample

My sample consisted of 4 participants who were practitioners or professionals who work with or around women with ADHD and a history of offending. I used a convenience sample of key informants. I collected this sample by utilising both personal and academic contacts I already had and contacting individuals who I thought might fit the inclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria were:

1. That the participants work or have recently worked with or around women diagnosed with ADHD and a history of offending.
2. This could include criminal justice workers such as police officers, prison guards, prison governors and judges for example.
3. It could also include practitioners or professionals such as therapists, counsellors or social workers.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Professionals or practitioners who only work around men
2. Those who have not encountered ADHD within their knowledge
3. Those who had left the job role working around women with a history of offending longer than 3 years ago.

The job roles of my final sample consisted of (n.2) police officers, (n.1) police and crime commissioner, and (n.1) therapist/counsellor.

3.3 Method

The method that I used to gather the data is semi-structured interviews. Semi-structured interviews are defined by Bryman (2016) as a “series of questions that are in the general form of an interview but is also able to vary in the sequence of the questions... Also, the interviewer usually has some latitude to ask further questions in response to what are seen as significant replies.” (p.201). I used this method so that I could collect data in which answered the questions I needed to be answered but also to allow participants to go into as much or as little detail as they liked on the topics in which they felt were relevant as well as those I considered to be relevant. I believe this will provide the most detailed and comprehensive data while also having some structure to guide the direction of the interviews and ensure it answers the research questions.

In the interviews, I aimed to gain information from participants on two main topics: the support available for women with ADHD and a history of offending, and the awareness and attitudes in criminal justice settings of ADHD in women with a history offending.

Interviews were conducted online, either on zoom or teams depending on which the participant preferred. I also recorded the interviews so that I can remain present during the interviews. The interviews lasted from 30 minutes to an hour I manually transcribed the interviews carried out on teams and used the transcription software on zoom for the interviews carried out on zoom. I then

analysed the transcripts using thematic analysis. Thematic analysis ensured that any significant categories or issues central to the discussion were picked up on (Denscombe 2021). I also looked for themes that emerged in the literature review during analysis such as awareness, diagnostic issues and SUD or drug misuse.

The below table provides further details regarding the interview participants and their demographic details.

PARTICIPANT NO.	AGE	GENDER	JOB ROLE	NEURODIVERSE
1	66	Male	Police & Crime Commissioner, Police Officer/Detective	No
2	39	Male	Police Officer/Detective & Public Protection Delivery Group	ADHD, Dyscalculia
3	35	Female	Counsellor	ADHD
4	24	Female	Police Officer	No

Figure 1. Table to show demographic information of participants.

3.4 Ethical Considerations

The possible benefits of research on society should outweigh the possible risks or harms. The British Society of Criminology (2015) has published a comprehensive ‘Statement of Ethics’ outlining the responsibilities of researchers and ethical considerations that must be addressed, including: harm caused, informed consent, anonymity, confidentiality, data protection and more. In addition, Bournemouth University (2012) has their own Research Code of Ethics that my research abides by.

I ensured that participants gave voluntary and informed consent with the use of participant information sheets and participant agreement forms. These forms also highlighted the participants right to withdraw at any stage of the research. However, if they withdraw after data collection, although all data will be anonymised and no new data collected, their data will not be withdrawn from the research to maintain the accuracy of the study. I have also safeguarded the privacy of

participants by keeping data secure in my password protected university OneDrive account and by anonymising all data before publishing it. Moreover, to maintain confidentiality, names and places have been anonymised to ensure participants are not identifiable.

Professionals and practitioners may feel that participating in this research may compromise their professional integrity and may jeopardise client/patient confidentiality. It may be difficult for them to manage the dual responsibility of providing valuable insights and a participant and maintaining confidentiality as a professional. Therefore, I ensured that I respected professional boundaries of the participants. Also, I reminded participants prior to the interview that they were free to answer questions in as much or as little detail as they liked, and they did not have to answer at all if they did not wish to.

An additional ethical concern is that the research leads to a further stigmatization of ADHD in women with a history of offending. To prevent this, I will be sure to find a balance between increasing and improving support and awareness and avoiding negative perceptions.

Chapter 4: Findings & Discussion

4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents and evaluates the findings from the data collected via 4 semi-structured interviews with professionals and practitioners who work with or around women with ADHD and a history of offending. These interviews were conducted in order to answer the research question: “How are women with ADHD and a history of offending supported?”.

Initial Code	Theme
Awareness	Awareness & Attitudes
Lived experience	
Training	
Ignorance	
Stigma	
Identification	Identification & Support
Diagnosis	
Adjustments and support	
Addiction & drug misuse	Deprioritisation
Having children	
Domestic abuse	
Exploitation	

Figure 2. Table to show initial codes & themes that emerged from the collected data

4.2 Awareness and Attitudes

Discussion around awareness and attitudes was continuously reoccurring throughout data collection. This theme includes general discussion around the awareness of ADHD, specifically in women and in the CJS; the attitudes towards ADHD in the CJS, specifically women with ADHD; and the factors which may influence or relate to the attitudes and awareness.

Upon discussion of the awareness of ADHD in women in the CJS, overall, participants agreed that it is poor. Levels of awareness in general were perceived as relatively low in the CJS, but more so for ADHD in women. This is demonstrated by the responses from participants when asked to describe the level of awareness surrounding ADHD in women in the CJS. Participant 1 described it as “appalling, while Participant 2 responded, “Poor. Very poor... ADHD in women, but then across neurodivergence, there is a poor level of understanding.” Moreover, this lack of awareness was also often discussed alongside “ignorance” surrounding ADHD in the CJS, particularly regarding ADHD in adults and women. Participant 1 explained the views which he has seen emulated across the criminal justice system. He described the attitudes across the CJS as largely “ignorant” and said that they “don’t understand it”. This ignorance is further highlighted when he spoke about ADHD in children in comparison to adults. He conveyed his views that the CJS and society focuses largely on ADHD in children and ignores it more in adulthood when he stated:

The state, society, takes the view that if a child has ADHD, or is on the spectrum range, they can intervene to change their education for the good. Once you’re an adult, this is just a personal view, but once you’re an adult, does it matter whether you’re ADHD or not? There’s nothing we can do. Which isn’t true as you know.

This highlights the significant misconception that ADHD ceases to be relevant or manageable in adulthood, which overlooks the ongoing needs and challenges faced by adults with ADHD. It is likely that this misconception derived from the historic view of ADHD as a childhood disorder which does not persist into adulthood (Cortese and Coghill, 2018). It has since been established however, that this is not the case and ADHD persists into adulthood in most cases (Cortese and Coghill, 2018)

Stigma and misconceptions surrounding ADHD were perceived as common. One example of this which was frequently mentioned was the stereotype of ADHD as a hyperactive “naughty schoolboy”. This stereotype was discussed on numerous occasions by participant 2 and participant 3. These two participants both have in-depth understandings of ADHD due to their job roles and also as they both have ADHD themselves. Their unique positions as participants who also have ADHD provides invaluable intel as their profound awareness of ADHD might allow them to notice stigma and

misconceptions more frequently than others. This stereotype of the hyperactive “naughty schoolboy”, which participants identified in the CJS, is harmful, particularly for adults and particularly for women. This is because those who do not fit this stereotype, such as adult women who often present more inattentively (Young et al., 2020), may not be identified as ADHD and therefore will not receive support for it. Additionally, the presence of misconceptions and stigma in the CJS was further demonstrated by Participant 2 when he stated that “You still have a lot of people who think it’s a made-up condition.” This misconception is likely to contribute towards the ignorance of ADHD in which has been established by this research. Moreover, Participant 1 stated that “because people don’t understand it [ADHD], ignorance tends to lead to stigma, abuse, [and] ridicule”. This demonstrates how the lack of awareness and ignorance of ADHD in the CJS play major roles in allowing stigma and discrimination to thrive. On the other hand, Participant 4 did not believe stigma and misconceptions regarding ADHD to be as common as the other three participants did. However, she said this may be due to the fact that ADHD is not commonly spoken about in the CJS. This further underlines the ignorance towards ADHD in the CJS. Although awareness was identified as poor overall, almost all participants recognised that it has gotten better over recent years due to an increase in the awareness of ADHD in the general public. This is positive as it indicates the ability of society and the CJS to change.

Participants all agreed that there was a lack of training specifically tailored to ADHD for criminal justice workers. When awareness was discussed, the lack of training was commonly thought of to be a factor contributing to the lack of awareness of ADHD in the CJS. This is mirrored by the findings of the CJI report (2021) which also found a lack of awareness and training amongst criminal justice workers. The CJI report (2021) did not, however, find levels of awareness to be even lower regarding ADHD in women like this study did, as it did not focus on women. Understandings of the training in place for the police varied slightly. Participant 1 stated that he was involved in introducing some training into the Police force he was the police and crime commissioner for: “I funded some specific training in [name of area] Police in 2016-17 to make front line officers aware of how to deal with ADHD and autism”. Meanwhile, Participant 2 said that he has not received any training prior to the month before the interview, and the training that he received from his police force was not mandated. Participant 3 said that she had received training, however, it was on neurodiverse conditions as a whole, not specifically ADHD, and it was not extensive. Additionally, Participant 1 discussed the lack of training among other CJS. Judges are not trained in ADHD and this is highly problematic due to the nature of a judge’s role: “I know all the judges in [name of area], they haven’t been trained in ADHD, they’re sentencing some people who have got ADHD without realising that there’s a big mitigation in their offending”.

The awareness that most participants had stemmed from their own lived experience. This was the same for the majority of other criminal justice workers due to a lack of training. Similarly, the CJI report (2021), found awareness to come from previous jobs or personal experience. Lived experience was recognised as important in understanding ADHD and how it affects people. Participants discussed that the interactions people have with ADHD, whether that be their own ADHD or ADHD in a friend or relative, shaped their awareness, views, and perceptions of ADHD. Participant 3 expressed that she believed knowledge based off lived experience to be invaluable: “For me, what I think is, is more valuable. Yes, there is training. But there is nothing more powerful than a lived experience or someone telling you their live experience.” Interestingly, lived experience was also identified to impact whether the non-mandated training is engaged in. Participant 2 stated that when he attended the non-mandatory training courses, he noticed that the majority of the people there were also neurodivergent. This is an issue as non-ADHD people do not have personal lived experience of ADHD and therefore, in general, might have a lower level of awareness than someone with ADHD.

However, there are challenges that come with awareness which is based purely off lived experience. Participant 2, who has ADHD himself, stated “most of my awareness comes from my own lived experience so as you can see, I am a white middle-class man, so that’s a lot of my awareness comes from”. And Participant 1 stated that the majority of his awareness that comes from lived experience comes from interactions he has had with men with ADHD. This highlights the subjectivity of lived experiences and the knowledge that is gained from it. If individuals have not received any formal training on ADHD, their knowledge of ADHD is likely to come solely from their lived experience. Consequently, they may make assumptions and generalisations about someone's unique experience with ADHD based on their own lived experience. These assumptions and generalisations are not likely to fit everyone’s experiences of ADHD, especially not women, highlighting the need for formal training.

The level of training of other criminal justice workers was not discussed as none of the participants worked in prison or probation services. However, the awareness and training of general practitioners (GPs) was mentioned. Participant 3 consistently recognised the lack of understanding that GPs have of ADHD, particularly in women, which poses a huge barrier to diagnosis. She mentioned how women with ADHD really have to push for help from a GP regarding ADHD otherwise “they just get palmed off”. This underscores the ignorance towards ADHD and demonstrates that this ignorance exists not only in the CJS.

Awareness was an area that all participants agreed needed to be improved upon within the CJS. It was suggested that more in-depth and mandatory training specific to ADHD should be implemented

across the CJS, as well as for other neurodiverse conditions such as autism, in order to improve awareness. Participant 3 also suggested that lived experiences should be integrated into this training by sharing multiple accounts from individuals with ADHD about how they experience it.

4.3 Identification and Support

Identification and support was a reemerging theme throughout the data collection. This theme includes the identification of ADHD and issues surrounding it, the diagnosis of ADHD and issues surrounding it, and the support surrounding ADHD for women with a history of offending.

The identification of ADHD was commonly discussed as an issue within the CJS. Participant 4 frequently discussed the challenges associated with identifying ADHD in people she interacted with as a police officer. On initial interaction, if she has been called to a scene, it is unlikely that she will know whether or not an individual has ADHD unless she has already come into contact with this individual before or if they disclose their ADHD. She says that in cases where an individual has not disclosed their ADHD “It's not easy to walk into a situation and be like, Oh, you have a neurodiverse condition.” Issues of identification are also worsened by the lack of awareness of ADHD in the CJS as CJ workers may not be aware of how ADHD can present, especially in women. Participant 1 also acknowledged that “the people in police stations aren't qualified to spot that [ADHD]”, further highlighting the need for training and presenting a need for screening. Participant 1 said that there is screening for individuals who come into the police station, however this consists of very simple questions and many people who have ADHD do not know they have it, therefore these questions often will not identify undiagnosed ADHD.

As previous research has found, ADHD is significantly underdiagnosed, particularly in women (Young et al., 2020). Participants 2 and 3 also commonly discussed that these women who are not diagnosed often go through the CJS with their ADHD completely undetected. Participant 3 has direct knowledge of this due to her unique position as a counsellor who deals with women with ADHD and a history of offending on a regular basis and will sometimes aid these women in getting their diagnosis. The lack of awareness of ADHD in women was a common discussion point when identification issues were brought up. Participants 2 and 3 mention how women whose ADHD does not fit the stereotype of the hyperactive “naughty schoolboy” are often undiagnosed and therefore unidentified:

We have a lot of women who are going completely undetected and also, we have these very antiquated, stereotypical views of what an ADHD person looks like. And that doesn't fit what a lot of the challenged of ADHD women in particular are

going though, because women, and I am slightly stereotyping here, tend to be much better at masking, falling into that inattentive category ... And it flies under the radar because they're not that stereotypical naughty boy that's drawing on the walls and jumping up and down and has those hyperactivity issues.

Due to these women, and some men, whose ADHD goes unidentified and undiagnosed, participants expressed a need for more comprehensive screening which should be put in place to identify ADHD in people who encounter the police. This is essential so that these individuals can be supported in the CJS and signposted to the correct services and then diagnosed and supported outside of the CJS as well.

Participants also established issues with the diagnostic process as well as with identification. Participants 1, 2 and 3 specifically, discussed the issues with the diagnostic services under the National Health Service (NHS) which are largely inaccessible. GPs who provide referrals for ADHD assessments are often unhelpful regarding women with ADHD particularly, but also men, and individuals seeking an ADHD diagnosis are often "palmed off" by GPs as previously mentioned. If an individual does manage to get a referral for a diagnostic assessment, the current wait list time is 2-7 years as identified by Participant 2. I can also confirm this from my own personal experience as I was put on a waitlist of 5-7 years for an ADHD assessment on the NHS after a lengthy battle with my GP to get a referral. Although these are not issues within the CJS, they are issues which impact dealing with ADHD in the CJS as well as wider society. Therefore, it was recognised by participants that this was something that needed to improve in order to improve the support that can be provided to those with ADHD in the CJS.

Once ADHD is identified in an individual within the CJS, whether that be via screening or prior diagnosis, they should then be appropriately supported. This research has found that there are some procedures in place in the police to support and safeguard individuals with ADHD. Participant 4, who is a police officer, spoke about the adjustments she might make for an individual with ADHD such as reading someone's statement back to them rather than them reading over their own statement. AAs were also mentioned by Participants 1 and 2, which can be used to safeguard and protect the rights and welfare of a vulnerable person. However, Participant 2 discussed a specific case which he investigated due to safeguarding concerns, where a woman with ADHD asked for an AA and her request was denied as "they didn't think it was serious enough to require that". This supports previous research on vulnerable adults and the use of AAs (Dehghani, 2016; Cummins, 2019). This participant then goes on to discuss a number of other issues with the CJS regarding supporting

individuals with ADHD “a lot of the structures, of policing and the criminal justice system not just policing, are designed for neurotypical people. And I’m talking about booking in procedures, the interview process, going to court, probation”. He also expressed that a lot of the time considerations are not taken into account by CJS workers, and he argues that this is harmful for a number of reasons. If someone’s ADHD is not taken into account during police interviews for example it may cause distress to the individual, but it may also mean the evidence collected is not from this individual is not of sound quality and therefore a conviction reliant on that interview may be unsafe. This is consolidated by Gudjonsson’s (2016) findings surrounding false confessions and ADHD.

Participant 1 however, felt as though the police do sufficiently safeguard these individuals. That being said, he was majorly concerned with the support provided after this stage such as in courts, prison and probation. This concern was expressed also by other participants too: “the juries aren’t alerted to it. They aren’t told you need to give compensation to this person... Jurors aren’t told courts aren’t told. It’s appalling”, “but they – to my knowledge – they don’t provide anything [support] in courts. And they certainly don’t provide anything in prisons.”

As well as the improvements that participants suggested should be made to ADHD screening in police stations and NHS services surrounding ADHD, participants also suggested improvements that could be made within the CJS to their safeguarding and support systems. Participant 2 who has ADHD himself, stated that having a “stim pack” or “something to distract themselves while in a cell” would be beneficial. He believes that if things like this were utilised then “when that person [with ADHD] comes out of that cell they’re going to be far more regulated”. He also expressed a need for more awareness and accessibility around AA’s so that people with ADHD can use them more often. Participants 1,2 and 3 also all stressed the importance of increasing the adjustments made in court for individuals with ADHD and increasing and improving the support and treatment for individuals with ADHD within prison and for them once they leave prison. However, as none of the participants work in courts, prisons, or probation, they could not offer deeper insight into these areas.

4.4 Deprioritisation

There were issues of prioritisation and deprioritisation that were discussed as well. This deprioritisation often occurred when factors other than a woman’s ADHD were prioritised and therefore her ADHD was either deprioritised or completely ignored. The main factors which were prioritised included children, addiction or substance misuse, domestic abuse, and exploitation. As previously discussed in the literature review, SUD and substance misuse are risk factors associated with ADHD (Breyer et al., 2014; Ottosen et al., 2016; Young et al., 2023). Victimization is also a risk

factor of ADHD. Women with ADHD are at particular risk of specific forms of violence victimisation such as intimate partner violence, domestic violence and sexual exploitation (Buitelaar et al., 2020; Young et al., 2020; Arrondo et al., 2023). This deprioritisation may further prevent women with ADHD from being identified and from getting the support they need for their ADHD within the CJS.

Children were commonly discussed as the priority within cases where mothers with ADHD have been involved with the CJS. Participant 1 stated that most of the women with ADHD who he encountered as a police officer and a police and crime commissioner, also had children which often complicated matters. Also, often the children would be diagnosed with ADHD and the mothers would not, further complicating matters. Participant 3 also stated that “if they've got children as well, it seems to be an automatic referral to children services” and then “there is very little support for mum and mental health”. This demonstrates how a woman may be deprioritised and subsequently not receive the help she needs. Children must be protected and safeguarded sufficiently in cases such as these, yet it is of equal importance that the needs of mothers dealing with ADHD and a history of offending are addressed. Research has found that when a woman’s ADHD is treated for, criminality can be reduced by 41% (Lichtenstien et al., 2012), therefore, offering benefits not only for these women but also for their children. Treating mothers for their ADHD may improve outcomes in the CJS not only for herself but also for her children as it may reduce reoffending rates and therefore provide more consistent availability and emotional stability for the children. This underscores the importance of prioritizing early identification and treatment of ADHD among women in the CJS. By focusing on effective interventions and support tailored to their needs, we can mitigate the impact of ADHD on maternal involvement in crime and improve outcomes for both mothers and children.

SUD and substance misuse was also a factor commonly associated with women with ADHD and was seen to complicate cases. Similarly to the findings of previous research (Ottosen et al., 2016), participants all discussed the common comorbidity of ADHD in women and substance misuse and recognised it as highly problematic. One problem which was discussed regarding substance misuse complicating interactions with the CJS was the identification of ADHD. Participant 3 recognised that for women with ADHD, addiction along with other issues such as anxiety and depression, often masks their ADHD and then when that individual seeks help for their mental health, ADHD is pushed to the side and not identified or treated. Similarly, Participant 4 also discussed the difficulty in distinguishing between SUD and ADHD: “as a person it's hard to know what is neurodiverse and what is drug addiction because she is a drug addict. She is very erratic within herself. So, it's hard to know what is neurodiverse and what is drugs essentially”. This is problematic as research has shown us that

treating comorbid disorders such as SUD without treating ADHD is often leads to poor functional and clinical outcomes (Ginsburg et al., 2014). This underscores the importance of ADHD screening, diagnosis and treatment for women with ADHD in the CJS.

Domestic abuse was discussed at length by Participant 4:

So, when I used to volunteer for the domestic abuse, charity as well, and counselling, supporting people through kind of getting out of domestic abuse situations. I'd probably say over a half, maybe even 3 quarters of my clients had ADHD, had brushes with the law offending, obviously with abuse as well. So yeah, there's there is a theme.

She spoke about how often these women who had ADHD, a history of offending, and a history of domestic abuse would encounter the CJS and their offending would be scrutinised, their history of abuse would be assessed, and then their ADHD would be completely ignored. This could be for one of two reasons: her ADHD was unidentified as the domestic abuse may have masked her symptoms, or it was ignored as it was seen as unimportant. Participant 3 spoke about one case in particular where a client with undiagnosed ADHD had been in an abusive relationship due to her “risk-taking behaviour” and the abuse along with her ADHD caused her to “spiral” which led to offending behaviours such as shoplifting, substance misuse, driving under the influence of substances. When she was caught by the police her abusive situation was used as mitigation to her offending, however, her ADHD was not identified and therefore not considered. It was only later on with the help of Participant 4 that she managed to get a diagnosis for ADHD and get treated for it. This particular case highlights the complex nature of the experiences which many of these women with ADHD and a history of offending have, and it underscores the need for sufficient ADHD services both within and outside of the CJS.

Deprioritisation was also emphasised by the discussion around the exploitation of young women. Participant 2 specifically, discussed the vulnerability in girls with ADHD around exploitation. He explained the risk of these young women getting exploited into involving themselves in “things around running drugs, county lines, but also the sexual exploitation as well”. But he also discussed the risk of these young women then being labelled as offenders instead of victims of exploitation. There is a lack of research on the exploitation of young women with ADHD. Some research has been done on the risk of sexual exploitation on this population (Young et al., 2020), however there is a gap in the literature surrounding other forms of exploitation.

Chapter 5: Discussion & Conclusion

This research aimed to identify the awareness of ADHD in women with a history of offending, and how these women are supported. Based on the qualitative analysis of four semi-structured interviews with professionals and practitioners who work with these women, it can be concluded that the awareness of ADHD in women in the CJS is poor, although it is improving; and the support available for these women in the CJS is extremely limited. The support that is available is often inaccessible as ADHD is not effectively identified in the CJS, specifically for women. The findings of this research are unique in that they shed light on the multifaceted challenges faced by women with ADHD and a history of offending in the CJS. The findings of this research presented interesting findings some of which were expected, others which were not. The poor level of awareness of ADHD in women was expected, however it had not been considered that due to the lack of formal training of criminal justice workers their awareness might be made up from their own subjective lived experiences. Moreover, the reference to factors which further complicate the cases of women with ADHD and a history of offending such as children, domestic abuse, SUD, and exploitation, were expected, but not to the extent which they were discussed by participants. The findings of issues regarding identification and diagnosis, and the lack of support however anticipated.

Overall, this research has highlighted an overwhelming need for change within and outside of the CJS regarding ADHD support. Within the CJS, more in-depth training on ADHD, along with other neurodiverse conditions, must be made mandatory for all criminal justice workers including police officers, judges, prison officers and probation officers. This training should improve the awareness of CJS workers on ADHD in general, but also on women specifically due to the lack of awareness and identification issues associated with ADHD in women. Also, a more comprehensive method of ADHD screening should be implemented in the CJS so that ADHD can be identified in individuals entering the CJS. These measures should be put in so that individuals with ADHD may be better identified and subsequently better supported. However, support must improve also. Within the police, adjustments should be made for individuals with ADHD to make it a smoother process for them, and also a fairer one. Things like stim and distractibility packs should be made available for individuals with ADHD while they are in custody and being interviewed by the police. Things like frequent breaks should be added during police interviews, and awareness and accessibility of AAs should be improved. This may help individuals with ADHD to remain more emotionally regulated, and also reduce the risk of false confessions, which is elevated for those with ADHD (Gudjonsson et al., 2016). Courts should also implement similar adjustments for individuals with ADHD, and ADHD should be considered more

during court hearings in case it is a relevant mitigating factor for the offending behaviour. This research has established that the support services for ADHD in prison and probation is also in need of improvement, however as none of the participants worked in the prison or probation services, detailed recommendations can not be made on how these services can be improved. Additional research must be undertaken to establish how these services can be improved to improve the outcomes of women with ADHD in prison and probation. Furthermore, ADHD services on the NHS should be improved to address the lack of diagnoses for women with ADHD.

The recommendations, as stated above, are based on the knowledge and opinions of the participants used in this study. However, although these participants have invaluable intel into this area due to their job roles and lived experience, they have not conducted an expert evaluation to inform these recommendations. This study is also limited by its sample size. Although the interviews were in-depth and detailed, the size of the sample might affect the validity of the findings. Future research, therefore, should be conducted to provide an evaluation of needs for women with ADHD and a history of offending. The generalisability of this study is limited as it focused mainly on women with ADHD, however, it provides new and necessary insight into women with ADHD and a history of offending.

In conclusion, this research addressed a significant gap in the existing literature regarding the support systems for women with ADHD and a history of offending within the criminal justice system. By exploring the experiences and insights of professionals and practitioners, the study highlighted the pervasive lack of awareness, inadequate training, and the detrimental impact of stigma and misconceptions. The findings underscore the urgent need for comprehensive training, better identification processes, and tailored support mechanisms to improve outcomes for this vulnerable population. Through these insights, this research provides a foundational step towards more effective interventions and policy developments aimed at supporting women with ADHD in the criminal justice system.

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Appendix 1: Interview Questions

1. Can you please describe your role?
2. Do you work with/come across women with ADHD and a history of offending on a regular basis in your line of work?
3. Do you receive any training or resources specific to ADHD awareness, specifically in relation to women with ADHD?
4. How would you describe your current level of awareness regarding ADHD in women who have a history of offending?
5. How would you describe the overall level of awareness in the criminal justice system regarding ADHD in women who have a history of offending?
6. How would you describe the overall attitude in the criminal justice system towards women with ADHD and a history of offending?
7. Have you come across any stigma or misconceptions regarding ADHD in women?
8. Can you share any experience or cases where you have encountered women with ADHD and a history of offending?
9. How do you perceive the availability and accessibility of support specifically tailored to female offenders with ADHD within the criminal justice system?
10. What sort of support is available for women with ADHD and a history of offending?
11. In your opinion, what gaps or limitations exist in the current support systems?
12. What challenges do you perceive in identifying and addressing ADHD symptoms in women with a history of offending?
13. What resources or training opportunities do you believe would enhance the ability of practitioners to support these women effectively?